

Metal Chelate Complexes of Thiosemicarbazone of Pyruvic acid

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Thiosemicarbazone of pyruvic acid has been used as a coordinating ligand. The complex compounds of the ligand with Cu(II), Ni(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Fe(III), Zn(II) and Cd(II) have been isolated in the solid state and characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility values as well as from electronic and vibrational spectral data.

GRINGRAS *et al*¹ studied the chelate-forming capacity of the thiosemicarbazones of some diketones. Bahr² suggested the structure of diacetyl-dithiosemicarbazone Cu (II). The present investigation deals with the synthesis of thiosemicarbazone of a carbonyl compound whose molecule contains an additional functional group situated at a position suitable in taking part in the formation of a metal chelate complex. Thiosemicarbazone of pyruvic acid was thus prepared and its performance as a ligand in forming metallic chelates was studied.

Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Fe(III), Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes of the ligand have been isolated in the solid state and characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility values, as well as from electronic and vibrational spectral data.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of thiosemicarbazone of pyruvic acid : To a suspension of thiosemicarbazide (0.1 mole, 9.1 g) in about 100 ml of water dil. acetic acid was added dropwise while heating on the waterbath until a clear solution was obtained. To this solution was added pyruvic acid (0.1 mole 8.8 g) drop by drop, followed by the addition of a few ml (5-10 ml) of ethyl alcohol. The resultant pale yellow solution was then refluxed for 2 hrs on the water bath when the colour of the solution became intense yellow. After the reflux, the yellow solution was concentrated to a small volume (30 - 40 ml) on water bath, cooled to room temperature and then refrigerated for several hours. The yellow needle-shaped crystals which separated out were collected on a filter, washed with aqueous ethanol and then dried in air.

The compound melts at 176° - 177° and is insoluble in water, benzene and chloroform, but is soluble in ethanol.

Found : N, 25.90%, C=29.48%, H=4.60%, S=19.54%, $C_4H_7O_2N_3S$ requires N, 26.08% C=29.82%, H, 4.35%, S, 19.87%.

Preparation of the metal chelates : Alcoholic solution of the thiosemicarbazone (0.1 mole) and aqueous solution of the metal chloride or acetate (0.05 mole) were mixed together when a deep coloured solution, often accompanied by the precipitation of a solid mass of the same colour, was obtained. The reaction mixture was heated on the waterbath for 5 - 10 mins with stirring and then allowed to stand at room temperature. The solid compound which settled down was collected on a filter, washed with water and alcohol and then dried in a desiccator over fused $CaCl_2$.

General Characteristics of the complexes : The metal chelates of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Fe(III), Zn(II) and Cd(II) were prepared by this method and they form highly coloured powders which are insoluble in water, alcohol, benzene and chloroform, but are completely soluble in dilute alkali producing a clear solution ; in the case of Fe(III) compound, metal hydroxide is precipitated with excess alkali. The compounds are all decomposed on heating with mineral acids.

The elemental analyses for nitrogen, carbon, hydrogen, metal and sulphur were done for all the complexes by the conventional methods. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made in a Gouy balance using $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ as calibrant.

The results are given in Table 1.

The electronic spectra of the compounds were taken in the solid state mullied with nujol in a 'Spectromom-20' (Hungarian) spectrophotometer and infrared spectra were recorded in the range of 4000 - 700 cm^{-1} in a Perkin Elmer machine.

TABLE-1

Compound	Colour	Found %					Calculated %					Magnetic moment in B.M.(30°)
		C	H	N	M	S	C	H	N	M	S	
[CuL ₂]	Blue	24.80	3.05	22.04	16.82	16.30	25.02	3.13	21.90	16.58	16.69	1.96
[NiL ₂]	Light-green	25.20	3.06	22.34	15.38	16.57	25.35	3.17	22.18	15.50	16.90	2.72
[CoL ₂]	Pink-red	25.25	3.10	21.95	15.34	16.53	25.33	3.16	22.17	15.57	16.89	4.85
[MnL ₂]	Yellowish-white	25.44	3.13	22.64	14.85	16.82	25.61	3.20	22.41	14.67	17.07	5.40
[Fe ₂ (OH)H ₂ O]	Pinkish-red	23.48	3.58	20.74	13.73	15.30	23.36	3.65	20.44	13.62	15.37	5.93
[ZnL ₂]	Light yellow	25.02	3.08	21.94	17.32	16.72	24.91	3.11	21.79	16.95	16.61	Dia-magnetic
[CdL ₂]	Light yellow	22.10	2.70	19.25	25.62	14.45	22.20	2.77	19.43	25.99	14.80	Dia-magnetic

L = a monovalent anion of the thio semicarbazone of pyruvic acid.

Discussion

From the stoichiometry of the metal chelates, it is apparent that the ligand, thiosemicarbazone of pyruvic acid, acts as a monoanionic species in forming complexes with metal ions. The infrared spectra of the ligand and the metal chelates taken in nujolmull were recorded to ascertain the points of attachment of the ligand to the metal ion.

The ligand shows three bands in the N-H stretching region viz. at 3380 cm⁻¹(m), 3220 cm⁻¹(m) and 3160 cm⁻¹(m) which agree well with those found in acetone thiosemicarbazone³; the sharp bands located at 1620 cm⁻¹ and 1700 cm⁻¹ are attributed to -C=N- and -COOH stretching frequencies respectively and although definite assignment for C=S vibration is difficult, it appears that the bands at 1090 cm⁻¹(m), 1025 cm⁻¹(w) in the free ligand are due to C=S vibration as suggested by earlier workers^{3,4,5}. There is no infrared band at 2560-2570 cm⁻¹ and this excludes the presence of thiol form of the ligand at least in the solid state and this is in agreement with the similar findings that open chain thiosemicarbazones exist in the thione form in the solid state⁶. In the i. r. spectra of the metallic complexes, the bands at 1620 cm⁻¹ and 1700 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand are shifted to lower frequencies viz. at ~ 1590 - 1600 cm⁻¹ and 1680 ~ 1670 cm⁻¹ respectively suggesting thereby that in the metallic complexes the bonding to the metal ion is primarily effected through azomethine and carboxyl groupings of the ligand. The complexes do not show any additional band in the 1600 cm⁻¹ region indicating that no extra -C=N- bond has been formed³ and thus excludes the possibility of 'thiol' form even in the complexes. The i. r. bands in the N-H stretching region do not alter significantly in the complexes except that the band at 3220 cm⁻¹ is shifted to higher frequency by 20-30 cm⁻¹ in general. Although the shift to higher frequency is difficult to explain, there is no doubt that the electronic environment of the -NH-gr. has changed³. No significant change in the stretching frequency for C=S vibration has been noticed in the metal complexes except that in [CuL₂], [NiL₂], and [CoL₂], the band at 1090 cm⁻¹ is extremely weakened, thereby indicating that the thiocarbonyl gr. has taken part in complexation in [CuL₂], [NiL₂] and [CoL₂] and in other cases, bonding from C=S gr. is excluded. The insolubility of the metal chelates in common organic solvents in general is probably due to the formation of polymeric species by intermolecular bridging either through acetato-carboxyl group or

through thio carbonyl group. The solubility of the metallic complexes in dilute alkali solutions are probably due to the fact that in alkaline solution, thio-keto form (Ia) of the ligand changes to the thiol-forms (I(b) or I(c)) where sulphahydril hydrogen is distinctly acidic and is replaced by sodium or potassium in forming soluble salts.

(Ia)

(Ib)

(Ic)

Electronic spectra and magnetic moments of the complexes

Copper (II) complex : The blue coloured copper (II) complex has a magnetic moment value of 1.96 B.M. which is well within the range of octahedral species^{7,8}. A tetrahedral stereochemistry is excluded as in such cases the magnetic moment value would have been still higher due to spin-orbit coupling^{7,8}. The electronic spectrum of the complex in the solid state show a broad asymmetric band centred around 16,600 cm⁻¹ indicating that more than one transitions are buried under the absorption envelope. A distorted octahedral structure is suggested for the complex with a symmetry lower than Oh⁹,

Nickel (II) Complex : The light green Nickel (II) complex has a room temperature magnetic moment of 2.72 B.M. which is somewhat a lower value than that usually observed for six-coordinate spin-free nickel (II) complexes¹⁰. In absence of magnetic data over a temperature range, nothing definitely can be said, but it appears¹¹ that a mixing of singlet and triplet states occurring in the complex, may be one of the possible reasons for this subnormal magnetic moment. The spectral bands located at $\sim 9,500 \text{ cm}^{-1}(\nu_1)$, $15,900 \text{ cm}^{-1}(\nu_2)$ and $26,300 \text{ cm}^{-1}(\nu_3)$ are assigned to three spin allowed transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively in Oh local symmetry^{12,13,14} and the shoulder at $13,500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to the spin - forbidden transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g(D)$ ^{14,15}.

Cobalt (II) Complex : The reddish pink Co (II) complex has a magnetic moment of 4.85 B.M. which is diagnostic of spin-free Co(II) octahedral species¹⁶. The absorption band at $\sim 20,400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition, the shoulder on the high frequency side (at $\sim 20,800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) being a consequence of the spin-orbit coupling in the ${}^4T_{1g}(P)$ state¹⁶. The band found at $9,260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is considered as the ν_1 band is due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ transition^{16,17}. No band due to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ as expected for Co(II) complexes in Oh symmetry is observed probably due to the weakness of the band and its proximity to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ band^{17,18}.

Manganese(II) complex : A magnetic moment value of 5.4 B. M. for the yellowish-white Mn(II) chelate is less than that generally observed for spin-free d^5 system. Such lower magnetic moments of Mn(II) Schiff-base complexes have been explained^{19,20,21} with the assumption of antiferromagnetic interaction between the manganese ions in the solids. The lower magnetic moment in the present Mn(II) complex may be either due to the presence of antiferromagnetic exchange interaction between the manganese atoms in the solid state or due to the aerial oxidation of Mn(II) \rightarrow Mn(III) during the preparation of the compounds.

In the absence of magnetic susceptibility data over a temperature range, nothing definitely can be said about the presence of antiferromagnetic interaction. Electronic transitions within the 3d configuration for 'spin-free' Mn(II) species involve multiplicity changes and hence they are very weak in intensity²². In addition to a number of very weak bands in the visible region the electronic spectrum of the present Mn(II) complex shows a somewhat stronger band at $\sim 25000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. A distorted octahedral structure is tentatively suggested for the complex.

Iron (III) complex : The pinkish-red ferric complex $[\text{FeL}_2(\text{OH})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ has a magnetic moment value of 5.9 B.M. which scarcely varies from the spin-only value as a consequence of the ground state ($6A_1$) being an orbital singlet²³. High spin Fe^{+3} d-d spectra are

generally weak and are frequently obscured by charge-transfer bands trailing into the visible region of the spectrum²³. The electronic spectrum of the present Fe(III) complex shows two bands at $13,800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $24,100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Besides, the compound shows a very sharp infrared peak at 3520 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the O - H stretching frequency of the hydroxo-bridge as suggested by Meek and Ehrhardt²⁴. Thus the complex may be given a polymeric octahedral structure.

The zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes are supposed to be tetrahedral as usual.

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